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Near-pole polar diagram of objects and duality

Abstract: The polar diagram of a set of points in a plane and its extracted dual EDPD were recently introduced for static and dynamic cases. In this paper, the near-pole polar diagram NPPD for a set of points is presented. This new diagram can be considered as a generalization of the polar diagram and has applications in several communication systems and robotics problems. After reviewing the NPPD of points, we solve the problem for a set of line segments and simple polygons in optimal time $2(n \log n)$, where n is the number of line segments or polygon vertices. We introduce duality for the NPPD of points and identify some applications.

Keywords: Polar diagram, Voronoi diagram Duality, Computational geometry Radar.

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